

Periodontal Cases

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1. Excision of Pyogenic Granuloma in A 57 Years Old Female Patient

A 57 years old female patient reported to the Department of Periodontology with the chief complaint of painless growing mass in lower anterior tooth region of the jaw. On examination the diagnosis was made Pyogenic Granuloma and the surgical excision was planned after 1 week of completion of scaling and root planning. The surgical excision was done by means of scalpel and the excised specimen was send for the histological report which confirmed diagnosis as pyogenic granuloma

Preoperative image

Intraoperative of pyogenic granuloma

Periodontal dressing

Excised Pyogenic Placed after excision of Granuloma Pyogenic Granuloma

Healing after 2 weeks

2. Lateral Pedicle Flap For Root Coverage of Miller Class 2 Gingival Recession

Patient of age 36 years came to the department of Periodontology with the chief complaint of sensitivity in the lower right front tooth region. On examination there was Miller Class 2 gingival recession with respect to canine of right side. Since there was a recession in a single tooth and the adjacent tooth width of attached gingiva was sufficient, hence Lateral Pedicle flap procedure was done as a treatment modality for root coverage of canine.

Preoperative image showing incisions

Intraoperative of Millers Class 2 gingival image recession in canine of right of Lateral Pedicle Flap Side.

Sutures placed after lateral sliding of flap towards Canine

Complete root coverage of right mandibular canine after 3 months.

3. Management of Ankyloglossia By Laser

Patient of 30 years reported to the department of Periodontology with the chief complaint of stammering of few words. On examination it was found that the patient had a mild tongue tie(ankyloglossia) of Class 1 (12-16mm). So this ankyloglossia was treated by soft tissue diode laser. Upon follow up after 2 weeks, the healing was uneventful and the patient stammering was reduced.

Preoperative pic of Mild ankyloglossia

Photograph of Soft Tissue Diode Laser

**Intraoperative Photograph
Completely Excised**

**Postoperative Photograph Showing
Lingual Frenum**

Healing After 2 weeks.

4. Gingival Depigmentation By Scalpel

A 26 years old female reported to the department of Periodontology with the chief complaint of black gums in upper tooth region due to which she was facing issues with her marriage. Upon examination, the color of her gingiva was pale pink with melanin pigmentation. Hence gingival depigmentation by scraping method by scalpel was planned in order to make her gingiva of upper tooth region pale pink in color. Upon follow up after a week, the pigmented gingiva become pale pink in color

Preoperative Photograph showing Melanin Pigmentation of Gingiva of maxillary Anterior tooth region

Healing after 1 week showing pale pink color of gingiva of maxillary anterior tooth region

5. Gingivectomy

A male patient of 46 years reported to the department of Endodontics with the chief complaint of broken anterior teeth in the lower region of jaw. Upon examination, the intraoral radiograph showed a periapical radiolucency with respect to right and left central incisor and lateral incisor of lower region of jaw with a poor prognosis. So extraction was advised followed by its replacement with the artificial crown. But the gingiva was bulbous in nature and required the gingivectomy and hence was referred to the department of Periodontology for gingivectomy of mandibular anterior region of jaw.

Preoperative Photograph of bulbous Gingiva of mandibular Anterior tooth region

Healing after 2 weeks showing the firmness of gingiva of mandibular anterior tooth region.

6. Canine Exposure By Laser

A female patient undergoing orthodontic treatment reported to the department of Periodontology with the exposure of right maxillary canine so that after exposure her canine will be retracted in its proper position by the department of Orthodontics. Laser was used and the right maxillary canine was exposed by creating a window by Laser.

Preoperative photograph of ectopically placed right Maxillary canine

Intraoperative Photograph showing, exposure of canine by Laser

Postoperative photograph showing the exposed canine with the placement of breggs bracket for retraction of ectopically placed right mandibular canine.

7. Management of Chronic Inflammatory Gingival Enlargement By Phase 1 Therapy

A 28 years female patient reported to the department of Periodontology with the chief complaint of swollen and bleeding gums in lower front tooth region. Upon examination, presence of calculus, the color of the gingiva was reddish in color, consistency was soft and oedematous, bleeding on probing was positive, contour was rolled out and blunt and surface texture was smooth and shiny and hence a diagnosis of chronic inflammatory gingival enlargement was made. Henceforth a thorough supragingival and subgingival scaling, followed by root planning and curettage was done. After two weeks follow up the gingiva reverted back to its normal clinical features.

Chronic inflammatory Gingival Enlargement with Characteristic features of Gingivitis

Resolution of normal features of gingiva after phase 1 therapy.